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Research Article

**FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
BUCCOADHESIVE FILMS OF LEVETIRACETAM FOR
TRANSMUCOSAL DRUG DELIVERY AND ASSAY BY USING
UPLC****C. Muralikrishna Goud^{1*}, Dr. Sumer Singh²**¹Research Scholar, School of Pharmacy and Medical Science, Singhania University,
Rajasthan, India.²Faculty of Pharmacy, School of Pharmacy and Medical Science, Singhania University,
Rajasthan, India.**Abstract:**

The aim of the present study was to formulate and evaluate buccoadhesive films of model drug, levetiracetam indented as an alternate route of drug delivery to have enhanced bioavailability. The bilaminated buccoadhesive films were prepared by solvent casting technique. Backing membrane was prepared by using ethyl cellulose, acetone, isopropyl alcohol and dibutyl phthalate where as drug loaded buccoadhesive membrane was prepared by using carbopol 934P, sodium alginate, distilled water and glycerol. All formulations of prepared films were evaluated for thickness, surface area, weight variation, mucoadhesion strength, folding endurance, chemical incompatibility and thermal studies. The invitro diffusion studies were conducted by using franz diffusion cells. Drug assay was carried out by developing a new method for UPLC.

Key words: Buccoadhesive films, buccal route, onset of action, first pass effect, dosage form

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INTRODUCTION:

Drug delivery routes for conventional dosage forms has many drawbacks and limitations. Oral route is most preferred route for the administration of conventional dosage forms like tablets, capsules, syrups etc, but first pass effect, solubility, instability in acidic environment resulting into inadequate and erratic drug absorption, frequency and increased dose administration, fluctuations in steady state concentrations etc are the drawbacks of oral route¹. Parenteral route of administration is the only established route that overcomes all these drawbacks associated with the inefficient oral route, but pain at site of injection is the drawback which is not preferred by many patients². Topical route facilitates only local action at the site of application. High molecular weight drugs, poor biological half life drugs, drugs sensitive to gastric environment, poor water soluble drugs, extensive first pass metabolism prone drugs require alternate approach for drug delivery³. Buccal route with bioadhesive approach is becoming more popular also facilitating dose termination. Buccal cavity was found to be the most convenient and easily accessible site for the delivery of therapeutic agents for both local and systemic delivery as retentive dosage forms⁴. Buccoadhesive drug delivery is relatively new drug delivery strategy;

in this traditional polymers are replaced by novel bioadhesive polymers such as Thiomers and lectins etc, to overcome limitation of traditional polymer. Buccoadhesive characteristics are factor of both bioadhesive polymer and the medium in which the polymer reside^{1,2 & 3}.

IMPORTANCE OF BUCCAL FILMS:

Buccal films may be preferred over adhesive tablets in terms of flexibility and comfort. In addition, they can circumvent the relatively short residence time of oral gels on the mucosa, which are easily washed away and removed by saliva. Moreover, in case of local delivery for oral disease, the films also help protect the wound surface, thus helping to reduce pain and treat the disease more effectively. An ideal film should be flexible, elastic, and soft, yet adequately strong to withstand breakage due to stress from mouth movements. It must also possess good bioadhesive strength in order to be retained in the mouth for the desired duration of action. Swelling of film, if it occurs, should not be too extensive in order to prevent discomfort.

DRUG PROFILE:

Drug profile of Levetiracetam is given in table 1.

Table 1: Drug profile of Levetiracetam

1.	Name	Levetiracetam
2.	IUPAC Name	(S)-2-(2-oxopyrrolidin-1-yl)butanamide.
3.	Molecular formula	C ₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂
4.	Molecular weight	170.209 g/mol
5.	Drug Category	Anticonvulsant
6.	Solubility	solubility in water at room temperature is 1.04 g/ml
7.	Bioavailability	100%
8.	Distribution	Levetiracetam modestly binds to plasma proteins (less than 10%).
9.	Metabolism	By liver cytochrome P450 enzymes, but through other metabolic pathways such as hydrolysis and hydroxylation
10.	Elimination	About 6 to 8 hours
11.	Effect of food	Decreases C _{max} by 20% and delays t _{max} by 1.5 hours.

METHODOLOGY:**Fabrication of buccoadhesive films:**

Buccoadhesive films are the films that adhere to buccal mucosa and delivers the drug to systemic circulation through internal jugular vein. These films contain buccoadhesive polymers that impart buccal mucoadhesion character to the films. The films can be prepared by suitable method based on the drug and excipients physicochemical property. Flexible films can be prepared either by solvent casting or hot melt extrusion technique to deliver drugs directly to a mucosal membrane. Direct milling, Solid dispersion extrusion, Semisolid casting and Rolling method are other methods of preparation of buccoadhesive films. Compared to creams and ointments they offer advantages in delivering a measured dose of drug to the site.

PREPARATION OF BILAMINATED FILMS:

Bilaminated films were produced by a casting/solvent evaporation technique using different combinations of polymers.

A. Preparation of backing membrane:

The backing membrane was prepared by dissolving ethyl cellulose (5%) in mixture of acetone and isopropyl alcohol (65:35), and 20% dry weight of polymer of dibutylphthalate as plasticizer. The plasticized ethyl cellulose solution was poured in to a 63 mm glass mould on level surface and solvent was allowed to evaporate at controlled rate by covering the mould with inverted glass funnel, to avoid blistering effect on dried films. The mucoadhesive

layer was prepared using different combinations of polymers as shown in Table 1. Both sodium alginate and other polymers were dissolved in double distilled water, after complete dissolution was over the drug was added. 10% Glycerin was added as plasticizer. The plasticized polymeric solution was poured in to mould containing a backing membrane and oven dried at temp of 40 dry weight of polymer of dibutylphthalate as plasticizer. The plasticized ethyl cellulose solution was poured in to a 63 mm glass mould on level surface and solvent was allowed to evaporate at controlled rate by covering the mould with inverted glass funnel, to avoid blistering effect on dried films.

B. Preparation of drug loaded membrane

1. The drug loaded membrane is prepared by using a beaker of 200ml and adding deionised water 100ml.
2. 1% sodium alginate was added to the above mixture and was stirred for about 1 hour in magnetic stirrer until it was completely dispersed to get a clear solution.
3. After that 1% chitosan was added to the above solution and was stirred in a magnetic stirrer until it was completely dispersed to get a clear solution. After completion of stirring with chitosan then 5g of drug levetiracetam is added to the solution and is allowed to stir on the magnetic stirrer for 1hr.
4. After that 10% glycerol was added to the above solution and was stirred for about an hour.
5. Then the solution was placed in a mould and was kept in hot air oven for 24hours at 50°C to obtain the drug loaded membrane.

Table 2 : Composition of levetiracetam loaded buccoadhesive film membrane (2 X 2 CM²)

SL.NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	Drug	200 mg	200 mg	200 mg
2	Sodium alginate	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg
3	Chitosan hcl	---	20 mg	40 mg
4	Glycerine	10%	10%	10%
5	Distilled water	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S

Q.S: Quantity Sufficient

CHARACTERIZATION OF BILAMINATED FILMS:**A. Physicochemical characterization of buccoadhesive films:**

1. **Weight:** The weight of the prepared films was determined by cutting the films into 2×2cm² size and shape then the weight was determined by using digital balance.
2. **Thickness:** The thickness of film is important for the brittleness of film. Thickness of each film was measured at three different locations on film using

a screw gauge and a mean value of five locations was used as a film thickness.

3. **Mucoadhesive strength:** The mucoadhesive studies were done on the buccal cheek membrane of the goat. The study was done by using-by-using NSAW triple beam balance. The goat's (Capra aegagrus hircus) buccal membrane was placed on a tile containing 6.8 pH phosphate buffer and pressed tightly. Prepared films containing drug was placed on to film and left for to develop mucoadhesion. The triple beam balance was allowed to adhere on to the surface of the buccal

membrane of the goat containing film. After sometime the beam attaches to the balance then the detachment strength of the film was determined by means of weight required for the detachment.

4. **Folding endurance:** Folding endurance of the patches was determined by repeatedly folding one patch at the same place till it broke or folded up to 48 times manually, which was considered satisfactory to reveal good patch properties. The numbers of time of patch could be folded at the same place without breaking which gave the value of the folding endurance.
5. **Drug content:** To determine the drug content uniformity, three film units of each formulation were taken in separate 100 ml volumetric flasks, 100 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added and continuously stirred for 24 h. The solutions were filtered, diluted suitably and analyzed at 209 nm in a UV spectrophotometer. The average of drug contents of three films was taken as final reading.
6. **Surface pH:** To determine surface pH of films, buccal films were left to swell for 1 h on the surface of the agar plate, prepared by dissolving 2% (w/v) agar in warmed isotonic phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 under stirring and then poured the solution into the Petri dish allowed to stand till gelling at room temperature. The surface pH was measured by means of pH paper placed on the surface of the swollen film.
7. **Swelling index:** For studying swelling properties, a drug-loaded film of $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ was weighed on a pre-weighed cover slip. It was kept in a Petri dish and 50 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added. After every five min, the cover slip was removed and weighed up to 30 min. The difference in the weights gives the weight increase due to absorption of water and swelling of film. The percent swelling, % S, was calculated using the following equation: percent swelling (% S) = $(X_t - X_0 / X_0) \times 100$, where X_t is the weight of the swollen film after time t, X_0 is the initial film weight at zero time.

B. *In vitro* permeation studies of Buccoadhesive films:

1. Construction of linear calibration graph of levetiracetam at wavelength of 209.

Buffer Preparation (6.8 pH):

Step1: preparation of 0.2M potassium dihydrogen phosphate:

Dissolve 27.218 grams of PDP in water and make it up to 1000 ml in a 1000ml volumetric flask.

Step 2: Preparation of 0.2M NaOH:

Dissolve 8grams of NaOH in water and make it up to 1000 ml in a 100ml volumetric flask

Step 3: Preparation pf 6.8 pH buffer:

5 Add 250 ml of 0.2M PDP into 1000ml volumetric flask.

6 Now add 112ml of 0.2M NaOH to the above 1000 ml volumetric flask, and make the final volume to 1000ml and mix well.

Preparation of drug stock solution by using 6.8ph buffer

Pipette out 10ml of the solution from the volumetric flask which contain 0.1g or 100mg of drug dissolved in buffer i.e., 0.1gram or 100mg in 100ml in another volumetric flask.

Make up 10ml solution by adding buffer water upto 100ml.

Then again pipette out 10ml of the solution from from the prepared solution and make it up to 100ml which gives 1mg/100ml concentration.

Now pipette out 1ml, 2ml, 3ml, 4ml, 5ml, 6ml, 7ml, 8ml, 9ml, 10ml of the solution separately, Mark them and add it to 10ml of volumetric flask and make it up to 10ml by adding the drug stock solution contains 100mg in 100ml

2. Diffusion studies:

Diffusion studies were performed by using two raw eggs which was firstly emptied. Then two egg shells were taken and placed in a beaker containing 15ml of concentrated HCL. After keeping it for 20mins the egg shell was dissolved and membranes was separated and was taken into another beaker containing deionised water to remove the traces of acid. After that the first egg shell membrane was taken into petri plate containing 6.8 pH buffer and the other shell membrane was taken into petri plate containing deionised water.

Two Franz diffusion cell were taken and washed using acetone and one was filled with buffer and the other with deionised water along with magnetic bead at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ degree Celsius on a magnetic stirrer. Egg shell membranes was cut into two by using surgical blade and was placed on the franz diffusion cell and the magnetic stirrer was switched on after sometime the film was added from the top of the franz diffusion cell and the samples were collected at regular time intervals using 1ml syringe. The study was performed for 8 hours and the absorbance of the collected samples was determined using UV Visible spectrophotometer.

C. Organoleptic characters of buccoadhesive films:

Organoleptic characters of formulated buccoadhesive films examined by physical evaluation.

D. compatibility studies

Chemical compatibility studies are performed to identify any possible interaction between the ingredients. Fourier transformer infra-red spectrum (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and

X-ray diffraction are the techniques usually used to conduct the compatibility studies. As shown in fig 5 and 6.

E. Assay by using UPLC: Assay was performed by using ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC). A method was developed by using solvent mixture for pure drug and the formulation sample tested for percentage purity.

F. Pharmacokinetics study: The plasma concentration and time profile curve to contrasts the plasma level profiles of levetiracetam after oral administration of the marketed tablet and buccoadhesive film (F3) formulations are shown in Table 6 and the various pharmacokinetic parameters are recorded. Buccoadhesive film (F3) was applied both sides to the cheek of albino Wistar rats. A dose of marketed tablet as the oral suspension was given to rats to evaluate the disparity in pharmacokinetic parameters with the buccoadhesive film (equivalent to marketed drug dose). The comparative results are shown in table 7.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Weight of prepared films: The film weight of all the three formulations are found to be satisfactory, comparatively F3 has shown adequate result (table 3A).

Table 3 A: Physicochemical characterization of buccoadhesive films (mean±SD, n=6).

Formulation	Weight In grams	Thickness in mm	Mucoadhesion Strength	Folding endurance
F1	0.081 ± 0.058	3.3 ± 0.5	0	47 ± 4.358
F2	0.083 ± 0.058	2.7 ± 0.2	38 ± 2	49.333 ± 2.08
F3	0.077 ± 0.058	1.88 ± 0.12	47 ± 5.567	51.666 ± 3.511

Table 3 B: Physicochemical characterization of buccoadhesive films (mean±SD, n=6).

Formulation	Surface pH	Surface area in cm ²	Swelling Index (ml/g)
F1	6.7±0.5	10.496 ± 0.004	19±0.12
F2	6.9±0.1	10.16 ± 0.001	28.2±0.24
F3	6.8±0.5	9.498 ± 0.009	42.5±0.81

Standard graph using 6.8 pH phosphate buffer:

Serial dilutions of drug in 6.8pH phosphate buffer has shown satisfactory absorbance at wavelength 209 using UV VISIBLE Spectrophotometer. Upon plotting a graph between concentration (X axis) and absorbance (Y axis) given in table 5, linearity has shown with R² 0.999.

Thickness of prepared films: The thickness of F1, F2 and F3 are found to be 3.3 ± 0.5, 2.7 ± 0.2 and 1.88 ± 0.12 respectively where as comparatively F3 has shown better result (table 3A).

Mucoadhesion strength of prepared films: Buccoadhesive strength of F3 found to be 47 ± 5.567 which is comparatively higher than other formulations (table 3A).

Folding endurance of prepared films: Folding endurance of prepared films was found to be 47 ± 4.358 (F1), 49.333 ± 2.08 (F2) and 51.666 ± 3.511 (F3) as shown in table 3A.

Surface pH of prepared films: Surface pH of prepared films was found to be adequate and in suitable range (6.7 to 6.9) with that of saliva as shown in table 3A.

Surface area of prepared films: Surface area of prepared films was found to be adequate as shown in table 3A

Swelling index of prepared films: swelling index of prepared buccoadhesive films was in the range of 19 -42, F3 was adequate with 42.5±0.81 ml/g.

Table 4 : Absorbance values of known concentration of drug in 6.8 ph phosphate buffer

SL.NO	CONCENTRATION (μ /ml)	ABSORBANCE
1.	0	0
2.	1	0.109
3.	2	0.12
4.	3	0.133
5.	4	0.148
6.	5	0.161
7.	6	0.178
8.	7	0.19
9.	8	0.204
10.	9	0.219
11.	10	0.231

Fig 1: Standard graph of levetirecetam using 6.8 ph phosphate buffer

Invitro diffusion studies: Results of *Invitro* diffusion studies of all formulations (F1 to F3) in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer are given in table 5 and found to be satisfactory.

Table 5: *Invitro* diffusion studies of all formulations in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer.

SL.NO	TIME HOURS	PERCENT DRUG RELEASE		
		F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0	0
1	0.0833	4.646 \pm 0.012	5.181 \pm 0.11	4.286 \pm 0.07
2	0.25	7.348 \pm 0.061	9.19 \pm 0.27	8.703 \pm 0.02
3	0.33	14.221 \pm 0.032	15.554 \pm 0.27	13.233 \pm 0.99
4	0.667	18.112 \pm 0.01	18.881 \pm 0.81	17.463 \pm 0.69
5	1	21.309 \pm 0.01	22.676 \pm 0.04	21.565 \pm 0.71
6	2	25.553 \pm 0.42	26.636 \pm 0.05	24.507 \pm 0.67
7	3	30.118 \pm 0.71	31.178 \pm 0.93	29.153 \pm 0.48
8	4	33.343 \pm 0.27	34.912 \pm 0.17	32.118 \pm 0.11
9	5	36.119 \pm 0.91	37.176 \pm 0.07	35.232 \pm 0.32
10	6	39.731 \pm 0.11	40.818 \pm 0.63	38.709 \pm 0.74
11	7	44.398 \pm 0.64	45.561 \pm 0.28	42.306 \pm 0.57
12	8	46.557 \pm 0.01	50.912 \pm 0.80	45.848 \pm 0.61

Fig 2: invitro diffusion studies of all formulations in 6.8 ph phosphate buffer.

Organoleptic characters of prepared films:

The organoleptic properties of all the formulations i.e F1 – F3 are found to be satisfactory. All the three formulations are palatable, where are the color of F1 is cream and translucent, color of F2 and F3 are brown. The odor of F1 is odorless and characteristic for F1 and F2, comparatively F3 has shown better result.

Table 6: Organoleptic characters of prepared films:

SL.NO	FORMULATION	COLOR	ODOR	TASTE
1	F1	Cream and translucent	Odorless	Palatable
2	F2	Pale brown and translucent	Characteristic (gum like)	Palatable
3	F3	Dark Brown	Characteristic (gum like)	Palatable

Drug and excipient compatibility: The spectrum of drug and excipient compatibility are given in fig no 3 and 4. No incompatibility was found.

Table 7: Comparative results of pharmacokinetic parameters (mean±SD, n=6)

Pharmacokinetic parameters	Marketed XR tablet (orally)	F7 Buccal
Tmax (h)	5	6.5
Cmax (µg/ml)	18.7	19.4
AUClast (µg.h/ml)	274	255
AUMClast (µg.h ² /ml)	295	285

Fig 3: FTIR spectrum of pure drug

Fig 4: FTIR spectrum of F3 formulation.

Fig 5: DSC of pure drug.

Fig 6: DSC of drug and excipients mixture.

Assay by UPLC: Assay was performed by using ultra performance liquid chromatography and the chromatograms are given in fig 7 and 8.

Fig 7: Optimized chromatogram of Levetiracetam.

Sl.no	Peak name	RT	Area	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Levetiracetam	1.113	1045602	2836	1.2

Sl.no	Peak name	RT	Area	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Levetiracetam	1.112	1038776	2473	1.11

Assay was obtained as 99.02% for Levetiracetam buccoadhesive film using UPLC.

CONCLUSION:

2x2 CM2 Buccoadhesive film formulations, F1, F2 and F3, containing 200mg of Levetiracetam were prepared by solvent casting method using chitosan and sodium alginate as buccoadhesive polymer and control release polymer respectively. All the prepared formulations were evaluated and the results of organoleptic characters, weight uniformity, thickness, surface area, buccoadhesive strength, diffusion studies and drug excipient compatibility were found to be satisfactory. F3 formulation has shown better results in all aspects compared to F1 and F2 implicating a positive indication for further studies.

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